

Using a Bayesian Network to Predict User Trust in Teleoperation Robots

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Abstract. Trust plays a crucial role in human-robot interaction (HRI), especially in teleoperation scenarios where users control robots remotely. This paper develops a static trust prediction model using a Bayesian approach to improve system design, user experience, and robotic reliability. By integrating prior knowledge with empirical data, we constructed a Bayesian model that estimates trust levels in teleoperated robotic systems. Our model incorporates physiological measures and task performance data to provide a comprehensive trust prediction framework. We evaluated the model’s performance using precision, recall, and F1 score, achieving high precision (0.92), good recall (0.84), and a balanced F1 score (0.79). These metrics demonstrate the model’s effectiveness in accurately predicting trust levels in teleoperated robotic systems. The results underscore the importance of trustworthiness in maintaining user confidence and improving system interactions. This study highlights the potential of Bayesian models in enhancing the reliability and user experience of teleoperated robots, offering valuable insights for future developments in HRI research.

Keywords: Trust, Teleoperated Robotic Systems, Human-Robot Interaction, Bayesian network

1 Introduction

Trust in human-robot interaction (HRI) is a critical factor influencing the effectiveness and adoption of robotic systems, especially in teleoperation scenarios where users control robots remotely. Understanding and predicting user trust can improve system design, enhance user experience, and increase the reliability of robotic operations. This study aims to develop a customized static trust prediction model using a Bayesian approach, leveraging both prior knowledge and empirical data to estimate trust levels in teleoperated robotic systems.

The concept of trust in teleoperated systems has been widely studied, and researchers have explored various dimensions and models to better understand how trust is formed, maintained, and sometimes damaged in these interactions. Some of them [4], highlight the complexity of measuring and developing trust in HRI, emphasizing the dynamic nature of trust and its dependence on factors such

as robot behavior, user expectations, and environmental conditions. Similarly, others authors, such as Yagoda [28], have developed a trust scale that assesses user trust based on dimensions, such as trustworthiness, perceived competence, and predictability. Considering this, Guo in [6] and [5] introduced Bayesian approaches to model trust dynamics, allowing us to predict different levels of trust as they fluctuate over time. In this work, trust is conceptualized not only as a static state but also as a dynamic construct influenced by the continuous interactions and feedback between the human operator and the robotic system. In this context, trust is considered a function of the robot’s ability to successfully complete tasks and the consistency of its behavior. Other researchers, such as Hoff and Bashir [10], have also explored the multidimensional nature of trust, arguing that it encompasses cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components, each of which plays a role in how trust is developed and maintained. human-robot interaction. The correlation between these components of trust highlights the complexity of trust in teleoperation systems that requires robust models that can accurately predict trust.

In our study, we developed a static trust prediction model tailored for teleoperated robotic systems using a Bayesian approach. By integrating prior knowledge with physiological and task performance measures, we estimate trust levels. The paper first reviews research related to trust in HRI, particularly in teleoperated systems. We then detail our methodology and the structure of our Bayesian trust model, followed by a discussion of the experimental setup and dataset used for the evaluation. Finally, we discuss the performance of the models and conclude with ideas and possible directions for future research on trust models in teleoperated robotic systems.

2 Related Work

Research on trust models in robotics has taken both static and dynamic approaches. Static models [28] evaluate trust by defined measures and user surveys, capturing variables such as reliability and perceived competences. These models capture an overview of trust at a specific point in time, but they may fail to account for changes in trust over time. Lee and See [13] explore how static models generally capture initial trust judgments but lack the flexibility to adapt to changing user experiences and system performance. In contrast, dynamic trust models consider the temporal evolution of trust. Desai [4] highlights the importance of dynamic models that adapt to changing situations and user experiences. These models frequently use real-time data, such as robot performance and human comments, to continually update trust estimates. Bayesian networks and reinforcement learning are popular techniques for creating these adaptive models, which can respond to variations in user trust caused by shifting robot behaviors and environmental conditions. Hoff and Bashir [10] discuss dynamic trust and emphasize the need for continuous calibration based on system feedback and user involvement. In the context of robotic teleoperation, cognitive load and trust have a direct link. High cognitive load might reduce trust

because users may feel overwhelmed and see the system as untrustworthy. Some authors [3] investigated how varying levels of autonomy in robotic systems affect user trust and cognitive stress. They discovered that offering adequate degrees of autonomy can boost trust while lowering cognitive tension. This finding supports the work of Parasuraman and Riley [16], who argue that mismatches between user expectations and system performance might lead to trust loss, especially in high cognitive load scenarios. Measurements of cognitive load in teleoperation often include physiological metrics such as galvanic skin response (GSR), blink rate, and facial temperature, with subjective assessments such as the NASA Task Load Index [8] [2]. These metrics assist in understanding the user’s mental effort and its effect on confidence during teleoperation activities. Increased GSR and blink rates, for example, typically imply increased cognitive load, which has been linked to decreased confidence. De Visser [26] provide an in-depth examination of these physiological measures, arguing that they are critical for real-time assessment of trust and cognitive load, especially in complex teleoperation scenarios. Modeling trust in technological contexts, especially in human-robot interactions, necessitates the integration of diverse data sources and modeling techniques. Bayesian networks offer a robust framework for combining prior knowledge with empirical data to estimate trust levels. These models can accommodate the uncertainty and variability inherent in human-robot interactions, providing a probabilistic assessment of trust. Additionally, Guo [6] and Körber [12] suggest that Bayesian models are particularly well-suited for dynamic environments where trust is shaped by both static and evolving factors. Apart from Bayesian networks, techniques such as fuzzy logic, machine learning, and reinforcement learning have been employed to simulate trust in dynamic situations. These approaches enable continuous adaptation of trust assessments in response to real-time feedback and changing conditions. Reinforcement learning, for example, can optimize robot behavior over time to gain user trust by learning from interactions and altering behaviors as needed. Xu and Dudek [27] demonstrated that machine learning models can anticipate trust based on user interaction patterns, allowing robots to alter their behavior proactively.

Overall, combining cognitive load measurements, dynamic modeling techniques, and real-time data analysis is essential for creating effective trust models in human-robot interaction. These models improve our understanding of trust dynamics and contribute to designing more reliable and user-friendly robotic systems.

3 Methodology

The goal of this study is to develop a static trust prediction model for teleoperated robotic systems. The model predicts a human operator’s trust level by analyzing factors such as physiological responses, task performance metrics, and interaction behaviors. Accurate trust prediction can enhance the safety, efficiency, and reliability of human-robot interactions, particularly in teleoperation scenarios where operators depend heavily on the robot’s feedback and perfor-

mance. This can lead to better system designs and more intuitive interfaces for effective teleoperation tasks across various applications, including hazardous environments. In our experiment, trust is a crucial factor influencing both operator performance and task success [21]. The user is tasked with remotely controlling a robotic arm to move two cylinders from their initial positions into a box within a two-minute time frame. More details about the experimental framework, the specific tasks, and the variables measured will be provided in the Experimental Section. This task was selected because it is a fundamental operation in teleoperation systems involving robotic arms, making it an appropriate measure for assessing trust. The simplicity of the task ensures that the focus remains on trust dynamics, providing clear insights into how trust levels impact task performance [7]. During the experiment, the following variables are measured:

- *T*: Trust level of the user, which is a discrete variable and is categorized into four levels based on the Human-Robot Interaction Trust Scale (HRITS) [17]: High Trust (4), Moderate Trust (3), Low Trust (2), and Very Low Trust (1). The Human-Robot Interaction Trust Scale (HRITS) is a validated questionnaire designed to measure users' trust in robotic systems. This scale assesses various dimensions of trust, including the reliability, predictability, and perceived competence of the robot. It is commonly used in studies involving human-robot interaction (HRI) to evaluate how different factors, such as robot behavior and performance, influence users' trust. [17]
- *CL*: Cognitive load of the operator, measured using NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [9], which is a discrete variable and can be Low (1), Medium (2), Somewhat High (3), High (4) or Very High (5). The NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) is a widely used tool for assessing subjective cognitive workload. Developed by the Human Performance Group at NASA's Ames Research Center, it evaluates perceived workload across six dimensions, providing a comprehensive measure of cognitive load during task performance. [9] [20]
- *GSR*: Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), also referred to as Electrodermal Activity (EDA), is a measure of the electrical conductance of the skin, which varies with its moisture level. This physiological signal is widely utilized in psychological studies and stress-related research to detect emotional and physiological arousal. GSR is particularly sensitive to changes in the sympathetic nervous system, which is activated during stress. GSR readings are continuous but can be discretized into intervals for practical applications. Based on the literature, GSR can be categorized into the following ranges:
 - **Low Arousal (Relaxed State) - 1**: GSR values are low in a relaxed state, typically with a skin conductance level (SCL) below 3500-4000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{minute}$.
 - **Moderate Arousal (Moderate Stressed State) - 2**: This intermediate range indicates a neutral state, with an SCL between 4000-5500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{minute}$.
 - **High Arousal (Stressed State) - 3**: High GSR values are associated with stress or anxiety, with an SCL above 5500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{minute}$.

These categorizations are supported by research on emotion recognition using GSR signals from the dataset presented in [23], stress detection using GSR sensors as outlined in [22], and the analysis of stress patterns from GSR data described in [1].

- *BR*: The blinking rate, measured in blinks per minute, serves as a crucial physiological indicator for assessing stress and cognitive load. Blinking, a semi-voluntary action, is influenced by emotional states, cognitive processes, and environmental conditions.

Blink rates can be classified into different ranges depending on the relaxed or stressed state of the individual. According to existing research, these ranges are:

- **Low blink rate (Relaxed State) - 1**: The typical blink rate ranges from 15 to 25 blinks per minute in a relaxed state. [19].
- **Moderate blink rate (Engaged State) - 2**: During cognitive activities, such as conversations or moderate tasks, the blink rate increases to approximately 26 to 36 blinks per minute. [19].
- **High blink rate (Stressed State) - 3**: Under stress, blink rate can increase dramatically, often doubling to around 40 blinks per minute [25] [14].

These categorizations are supported by studies of blink patterns under stressful conditions [25] and the relationship between blink rate and cognitive load [14].

- *P*: The performance variable is used to measure the success or failure of the user in completing a given task. It is a binary variable with two possible values:
 - **Success (1)**: Indicates that the user successfully completed the task within the given constraints and criteria.
 - **Failure (0)**: Indicates that the user did not complete the task successfully, either due to time constraints, errors, or inability to achieve the task objectives.
- *SO*: The Spatial Orientation Test (SOT) is a well-established cognitive assessment tool designed to measure an individual’s ability to perceive and mentally manipulate spatial relationships. This test is key to understand spatial thinking and orientation skills, which are critical in various fields such as navigation, architecture, and robotics [11]. In this case, the variable is measured continually with a range from 0 to 180 degrees representing the error of the user trying to allocate one or more objects in the simulation. Values closer to 180 indicate lower spatial skill.
- *Temp*: Facial temperature, particularly changes in the temperature of key facial areas like the cheeks, forehead, and nose, is a significant indicator of cognitive load and emotional states such as trust. Thermal imaging allows for the continuous monitoring of these temperature changes, providing insights into the user’s physiological responses during tasks. Facial temperature measurement is a non-invasive method to gauge cognitive and emotional states, crucial for applications in human-robot interaction, user experience design, and psychological studies. Lower trust is associated with greater temperature

fluctuations, with significant drops in the nose area [15] [24]. Research indicates that an increase in cognitive load often corresponds with a decrease in facial temperature, particularly around the nose and forehead. Typical ranges of higher cognitive load show a decrease of 1–2°C in these areas [2]. This can result in a temperature decrease of up to 1.5°C compared to relaxed states. In this case, we took the average of the slopes of temperature changing of each region of interest as forehead, nose, and cheeks. The slope and the average are calculated using the following:

$$S = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{T_{i+1} - T_i}{t_{i+1} - t_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

where S is the average slope of temperature change, T_i and T_{i+1} are the temperatures at time points t_i and t_{i+1} respectively, and n is the number of time intervals.

The trust level T is affected by these observed factors, and we aim to model these relationships using a Bayesian Network. Measurements and trust estimations are conducted offline after each experiment, ensuring the model reflects the static nature of trust during the interaction. The joint probability distribution of all variables is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P(T, CL, GSR, BR, P, SO, Temp) &= P(T|CL, GSR, BR, P, SO, Temp) \\ &P(CL|GSR, BR, P, SO, Temp) \quad (2) \\ &P(GSR)P(BR)P(P)P(SO)P(Temp) \end{aligned}$$

By applying Bayesian inference, we aim to calculate the posterior probability distribution of trust levels based on the evidence observed in the experiments. This model will enable us to predict the operator’s trust level with high accuracy, providing a deeper understanding of how different factors influence trust in teleoperated robotic systems. Ultimately, the trust estimation model is expected to enhance the design and implementation of teleoperated robots by ensuring they can adapt to the trust dynamics of human operators. This will lead to more efficient and reliable human-robot interactions.

4 Trust model prediction

In our model, the trust level T is influenced by several observed variables: cognitive load CL , Galvanic Skin Response GSR , Blink Rate BR , performance P , spatial orientation test result SO , and facial temperature $Temp$. The cognitive load CL is dependent on the measurements of GSR , BR , P , SO , and $Temp$. This structure reflects the interdependencies of these variables and their collective impact on trust.

Given observations (evidence) about the variables, we can use Bayesian inference to update our belief about T . The posterior probability of T given the evidence is calculated using Bayes’ theorem:

$$P(T|\text{evidence}) = \frac{P(\text{evidence}|T)P(T)}{P(\text{evidence})} \quad (3)$$

The conditional probability of trust T given the observed variables can be expressed as:

$$P(T|GSR, BR, Temp, P, SO, CL) = \frac{P(T)P(GSR|T)P(BR|T)P(Temp|T)}{P(GSR, BR, Temp, P, SO, CL)} \frac{P(P|T)P(SO|T)P(CL|GSR, BR, Temp, P, SO, T)}{P(GSR, BR, Temp, P, SO, CL)} \quad (4)$$

where:

- $P(T|GSR, BR, Temp, P, CL, SO)$ is the posterior probability of trust given the observed variables.
- $P(T)$ is the prior probability of trust.
- $P(GSR|T)$, $P(BR|T)$, $P(Temp|T)$, $P(P|T)$, and $P(SO|T)$ are the likelihoods of the observed variables given trust.
- $P(CL|GSR, BR, Temp, P, SO, T)$ is the conditional probability of cognitive load given the other variables and trust.
- $P(GSR, BR, Temp, P, CL, SO)$ is the marginal probability of the observed variables.

Parameter estimation combines prior information about parameters with the likelihood of the observed data to obtain a posterior distribution of the parameters. For the trust variable T , we assume a Beta distribution suitable for modeling probabilities.

Given a set of observations $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and a parameter θ :

$$P(\theta|X) = \frac{P(X|\theta)P(\theta)}{P(X)} \quad (5)$$

where $P(\theta|X)$ is the posterior distribution, $P(X|\theta)$ is the likelihood, $P(\theta)$ is the prior distribution, and $P(X)$ is the marginal likelihood.

For a Beta distribution, the prior $P(\theta)$ is:

$$P(\theta) \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta) \quad (6)$$

Using Bayes' theorem:

$$P(\theta|X) = \frac{P(X|\theta)P(\theta)}{P(X)} = \frac{P(X|\theta)P(\theta)}{\int_{\Theta} P(X|\theta)P(\theta)d\theta} \quad (7)$$

It means that by the end of the experiment the trust of each participant could be calculated as:

$$T \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha^*, \beta^*) \quad (8)$$

Where α^* and β^* are the parameter estimated using the apriori conditional table and the experimental data.

The Bayesian model allows us to integrate prior beliefs about the relationships between variables using sample data. By calculating posterior distributions for each parameter based on the observed data, we update our initial hypotheses with empirical evidence. This method ensures that our predictions are not only based on data but also reflect prior knowledge and research on the topic.

5 Experiment and Dataset

Fig. 1: General view of the system. Optitrack system and UR5 Husky. Position of the cameras that the user saw in each condition

For this study, we used a UniversalRobots™ UR5 manipulator robot mounted on a Husky™ mobile robotic platform, which remained static in our setup. The UR5, with its six degrees of freedom (DoF), offers precise manipulation capabilities and a reach of 0.85 meters, making it well suited for our tasks. Teleoperation was facilitated by a 6-degree-of-freedom joystick, and we used the OptiTrack real-time tracking system to precisely measure distances between the robotic arm’s gripper and the cylinders, that are part of the task the user must complete. The OptiTrack system provided accurate positional data necessary to assess user performance and trust in the robotic system under varying conditions of incomplete information.

During the experiment, RGB and thermal cameras recorded participants’ facial features. We used a Logitech HD C930e webcam for RGB images and a USB-powered Optris PI 640i infrared camera for thermal images. These cameras were mounted on an octopus-style tripod. In addition, we measured each participant’s galvanic skin response (GSR) using Shimmer3 GSR+ units. These noninvasive sensors provided real-time data on skin conductance, reflecting physiological activation associated with cognitive load.

Participants completed several questionnaires before and after each experimental condition. At baseline, they completed a demographic form, the Big Five Personality Inventory (short form) [18], and the Spatial Orientation Test (SOT). After each condition, they completed the NASA Task Load Index (TLX) and the

Human-Robot Interaction Trust Scale (HRITS). These questionnaires provided valuable information about individual differences and the impact of experimental conditions on cognitive load and confidence.

In the experimental scenario, participants controlled the UR5 robotic arm to place two wood cylinders inside a box, representing a very common geometric form to manipulate in this type of scenarios, as it is shown in the Figure 1. The task had to be completed within two minutes, based on visual information from three cameras. The camera images were frozen 30 seconds after the start of the task, creating an incomplete information situation. The experiment included three separate conditions to assess the impact of different levels of guidance on user performance and confidence. The user completed each condition only once during the experiment—there was no training phase for the participants. The conditions included no guidance, verbal guidance (T2S with the distance between the robot and the goal), and a combination of verbal and visual guidance T2S with the distance between the robot and the goal + 3D GUI indicating the direction to move the robot with the cylinders).

We collected several metrics to assess task performance, including success rates, completion times, blink frequency, and GSR data. Thermal and RGB images were processed offline, and facial temperatures were extracted using the ROS Optris Drivers node and the Dlib facial expression library. Blink frequency and GSR features such as cumulative GSR and spike count were measured to assess cognitive load and stress during tasks. This comprehensive data collection allowed us to model the relationship between these factors and the human operator’s confidence level.

A total of twenty-eight people participated in this experiment, including 14 women and 14 men, all students and administrative members of the Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IP Paris). The age distribution is as follows: 64% (18 participants) are between 20 and 28 years old, 14% (4 participants) are between 28 and 36 years old and 22% (6 participants) are over 36 years old. It is important to clarify that for each participant, this was a completely new setup, and they had only one opportunity to complete the task under each condition. In total, each participant controlled the robot on three separate occasions.

To develop and validate the trust prediction model, we employed a cross-validation technique by splitting the collected data into training and testing sets. Specifically, 75% of the data was used to train the model, allowing it to learn the relationships between observed factors and trust levels. The remaining 25% of the data was reserved for testing the model’s accuracy, ensuring that the evaluation was conducted on unseen data. In the testing phase, the model’s predictions were compared to the actual trust levels reported by participants.

6 Results and Discussion

We compute a conditional probability table (CPT) and use it to estimate a Bernoulli probability distribution for trust purposes. This involved using the prior probabilities from the CPT to train our model. Using the derived prob-

ability distribution, we were able to make predictions about trust levels in the teleoperated robotic system. This approach allowed us to incorporate both empirical data and prior knowledge to provide robust trust predictions.

6.1 Conditional Probability Table

To construct the conditional probability table (CPT) for our Bayesian model, we first collect frequency data for the observed variables in our experiments. We count the occurrences of each combination of variables and their states. At the end of each experiment, we take measurements of the physiological and task performance variables to calculate the frequencies needed for the conditional probability table (CPT). These frequencies are then used to estimate the conditional probabilities and subsequently the trust levels.

We then calculated the conditional probabilities by dividing the frequency of each combination by the total number of observations.

For instance, consider the calculation for the conditional probability:

$$\begin{aligned} P(T = 1 | GSR = 0, BR = 0, Temp = Y^\circ C, CL = 0, P = 0, SO = X^\circ) &= \\ &= \frac{\text{Frequency of } (T = 1)}{\text{Total Frequency}} = \frac{5}{20} = 0.25 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

This process was repeated for all combinations of the variables to complete the CPT, providing the necessary conditional probabilities for the Bayesian Network model. The conditional probability table for the variables and their relationship with trust is summarized below:

Variable	Trust (T)=1	Trust (T)=2	Trust (T)=3	Trust (T)=4
GSR=1	0.0	0.04	0.18	0.78
GSR=2	0.0	0.25	0.75	0
GSR=3	0.1	0.56	0.34	0.0
BR=1	0.0	0.22	0.78	0
BR=2	0.1	0.46	0.44	0
BR=3	0.0	0.74	0.19	0.07
Temp= $Y^\circ C$	$\mathcal{N}(1.15^\circ C, 0.14^\circ C)$	$\mathcal{N}(0.94^\circ C, 0.18^\circ C)$	$\mathcal{N}(0.75^\circ C, 0.16^\circ C)$	$\mathcal{N}(0.73^\circ C, 0.19^\circ C)$
P=0	0.25	0.55	0.15	0.05
P=1	0.0	0.15	0.55	0.3
CL=1	0	0.05	0.2	0.75
CL=2	0	0	0.35	0.65
CL=3	0	0.45	0.55	0
CL=4	0	0.6	0.4	0
CL=5	0.16	0.74	0.1	0
SO= X°	$\mathcal{N}(74.05^\circ, 12.32^\circ)$	$\mathcal{N}(51.20^\circ, 5.23^\circ)$	$\mathcal{N}(23.01^\circ, 10.34^\circ)$	$\mathcal{N}(11.23^\circ, 3.21^\circ)$

Table 1: Conditional Probability Table (CPT) for variables and their relationship with trust

When dealing with continuous variables like temperature and the Spatial Orientation Test (SOT), it is essential to summarize these variables using their probability distributions instead of discretizing them into categories. By providing the parameters of these distributions (e.g., mean and standard deviation for a Gaussian distribution), we can effectively describe the relationship between these continuous variables and trust levels. This method offers a detailed representation of how temperature and SOT scores vary with trust, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of their impact without oversimplifying the data.

6.2 Estimation of $P(\theta)$

Using the conditional probability values from the CPT, we estimated the probability of trust for each individual using a Beta distribution. Trust probability was calculated by fitting a Beta distribution to the observed data, with parameters $\alpha = 0.13$ and $\beta = 0.28$ derived from the data. This continuous probability distribution reflects varying trust levels based on the observed variables.

To estimate the Beta distribution parameters for the trust variable using the Conditional Probability Table (CPT), we begin by gathering frequency data that detail the occurrences of each trust level given the observed variables. Using this data, we compute the mean (μ) and variance (σ^2) of the trust levels, which are essential for determining the Beta distribution parameters. The parameters α and β are derived using the method of moments. These parameters allow the Beta distribution to accurately model the probability of different trust levels based on the observed data, providing a nuanced understanding of trust in the teleoperated robotic system.

The parameters α and β are calculated as follows:

$$\alpha = \mu \left(\frac{\mu(1-\mu)}{\sigma^2} - 1 \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\beta = (1-\mu) \left(\frac{\mu(1-\mu)}{\sigma^2} - 1 \right) \quad (11)$$

The Beta distribution for trust provides a continuous probability distribution, reflecting the varying levels of trust based on the observed variables. The parameters of the Beta distribution for the trust variable were estimated as follows: $\alpha = 0.13$ and $\beta = 0.28$. Also in Figure 2, it can be seen how the levels of trust are distributed using this estimation. The estimated Beta distribution parameters and the corresponding graph reveal that trust levels tend to polarize towards the extremes. This indicates that depending on the conditions, tasks, and physiological variables, an individual's trust in the system can either decrease significantly or be very high. Trust is less likely to be moderate or medium. Furthermore, people tend to quickly lose trust if the system fails or crashes, highlighting the sensitivity of trust in system reliability. Even minor errors can significantly reduce trust levels. The shape of the distribution indicates that trust is more likely to be found at the extremes, either very high or very low, rather than at moderate levels. This polarization suggests that users tend

to form strong opinions about the system’s reliability, with minor errors significantly reducing trust while consistent performance can enhance it substantially. This insight emphasizes the importance of maintaining high system reliability to foster user trust.

Fig. 2: Beta estimation for the levels of trust

6.3 Predictions results

To evaluate the performance of our trust prediction model, we used standard metrics: precision, recall, and F1 score. These metrics provide insights into the accuracy and effectiveness of the model in predicting trust levels in teleoperated robotic systems. Precision measures the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions. In our context, it indicates how many of the trust predictions made by the model were actually correct, having a value of 92%. Recall measurement reflects the model’s ability to identify all relevant instances of trust, having in this case a value of 0.84. The F1 score provides a single metric that balances both precision and recall, having in this case a value of 0.79 indicates a good balance, reflecting the overall effectiveness of the model. The results were obtained using 25% of the data reserved for testing, ensuring evaluation on unseen data.

7 Conclusions

In this study, we developed a customized static trust prediction model for teleoperated robots using a Bayesian approach. By incorporating prior beliefs and empirical data, we created a comprehensive conditional probability table (CPT) and used a Beta distribution to estimate trust levels. Our results indicate that trust levels tend to be biased toward the extremes, either significantly high or low, across various conditions, tasks, and physiological variables. The model’s

performance was evaluated using precision, recall, and F1 score, with results demonstrating high precision (0.92), good recall (0.84), and a balanced F1 score (0.79). Despite these promising results, our study has certain limitations. The static nature of the model restricts its ability to adapt to trust dynamics over time, potentially limiting its applicability in long-term interactions or varying operational contexts. Future work should focus on developing dynamic trust models that can account for real-time changes in user trust, thus providing a more nuanced and adaptive prediction framework. Future research could integrate machine learning with Bayesian methods to enhance trust predictions and reduce sensitivity to extreme levels, improving the reliability and user experience of teleoperated robots and advancing human-robot interactions.

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